

LET'S **OPEN** SCIENCE!

The Open Science Support Centre offers the following to employees and students of Charles University:

- Tailor-made training and individual consultations
- Methodological support in selecting a suitable open access journal or repository
- Methodological support in examining a potentially predatory journal or publisher
- Methodological support in research data management before, during and after the project
- Methodological support in providing open access to research data

More information about open science can be found at openscience.cuni.cz or you can contact us at openscience@cuni.cz.

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